

INVESTIGATION THE EFFECT OF LOADS ON THE DEFORMATION OF THE PLATE

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Abstract. In the article rectangular with constant thickness under the influence of variable forces the process of deformation of a structural element in the form of a thin plate and the calculation of the transverse vibrations of the plate under the influence of evenly distributed loads on this surface , as well as the study of these processes and the analysis of the obtained results are devoted to.

Key words: plate, variable forces, deformation, rectangular plate, plate bending equation, equations of motion, transverse forces, surface, thin plate, transverse vibrations, elastic .

Аннотация. В статье опрѳмоугольный с постоянной толщиной под действием переменных сил оно посвящено расчету процессов деформирования элемента конструкции в виде тонкой пластины и поперечных колебаний пластины под действием равномерно распределенных нагрузок на эту поверхность, а также исследованию этих процессов и анализу полученных результатов.

Ключ слова: пластина , переменные силы, деформация , прямоугольная пластина, пластина наклонившись уравнение, уравнения движения, поперечные силы, поверхность, тонкая пластина, поперечные колебания, упругие.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada o`zgaruvchan kuchlar ta'sirida o`zgarmas qalinlikdagi to`g`ri burchakli yupqa plastinka shaklidagi konstruktiv elementning deformatsiyalanishi jarayonlari va bu sirti bo`yicha tekis taqsimlangan yuklanishlar

ta'sirida bo'lgan plastinkaning ko'ndalang tebranishlarini hisoblash, shuningdek bu jarayonlarni tadqiq etish, hamda olingan natijalarni taxlil qilishga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlari: plastinka, o'zgaruvchan kuchlar, deformatsiyalanish, to'g'ri burchakli plastinka, plastinka egilish tenglamalari, harakat tenglamalari, ko'ndalang kuchlar, sirt, yupqa plastinka, ko'ndalang tebranishlar, elastik.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, information and communication technologies have penetrated into the intellectual activity of people and are one of the main reasons for the growth of scientific and technical development. Development of modern new techniques and technologies made it necessary to study the issues of deformation and vibration of a thin plate under the influence of impulse forces .

Thin plate deformation and vibration until now, it has a very important practical effect and is applied to various fields of modern technology. Implementation of these tasks, including issues of thin plate deformation and vibration is one of the important issues, and in this regard, improvement of research methods is important.

MAIN PART

Deformation of a plate under the influence of impulse forces of constant thickness . We use the hypothesis that the normal of the middle surface of the plate does not change even for the next case of deformation. According to the Cauchy relation,

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}; \quad \varepsilon_y = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}; \quad \gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

the 1st part of the expression (1) y by 2 times, the second one x by two times, and the third one by one x and one time y , we get the equations of continuity of double deformations:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_x}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_y}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} = 0 \tag{2}$$

The relationship between stress and strain for an elastic plate is according to the generalized Hooke's law

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{1}{E}(\sigma_x - \mu\sigma_y); \varepsilon_y = \frac{1}{E}(\sigma_y - \mu\sigma_x); \gamma_{xy} = \frac{2(1+\mu)}{E} \tau_{xy} \tag{3}$$

here E - modulus of elasticity, μ - Poisson's coefficient. Putting expressions (3) into equation (2), we get the following.

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \sigma_y}{\partial x} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \tau_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} - \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_x}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \tau_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} \right) = 0 \tag{4}$$

The equilibrium differential equation is according to Fig. 1

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + X &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial^2 \sigma_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + Y &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where X and Y are volume forces.

volumetric forces $X \equiv Y \equiv 0$, we introduce the stress function satisfying equation (5) Φ .

$$\sigma_x = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2}; \quad \sigma_y = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2}; \quad \tau_{xy} = - \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x \partial y}; \tag{6}$$

Figure 1. Normal and tensile stresses in the plate in case of plane stress

Substituting (6) into (4), we get the following

$$\frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial y^4} = 0 \quad (7)$$

or

$$\nabla^2 \nabla^2 \Phi = 0 \quad (8)$$

where $\nabla^2 \nabla^2$ the -biharmonic operator:

$$\nabla^2 \nabla^2 = \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right) = \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4}{\partial y^4} \quad (9)$$

Solving equation (8), stresses can be found from formula (6), strains according to Hooke's law (3), by integrating (1) and taking into account the boundary conditions, displacements are found.

If we take the expression of Hooke's law with respect to stresses when the volumetric forces are non-zero,

$$\sigma_x = \frac{E}{1-\mu^2} (\varepsilon_x + \mu \varepsilon_y); \quad \sigma_y = \frac{E}{1-\mu^2} (\varepsilon_y + \mu \varepsilon_x); \quad \tau_{xy} = \frac{E}{2(1+\mu)} \gamma_{xy} \quad (10)$$

If we add (5) to the equilibrium equation;

$$\frac{E}{1-\mu^2} \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon_x}{\partial x} + \mu \frac{\partial \varepsilon_y}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{E}{2(1+\mu)} \frac{\partial \gamma_{xy}}{\partial y} + X = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{E}{1-\mu^2} \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon_y}{\partial y} + \mu \frac{\partial \varepsilon_x}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{E}{2(1+\mu)} \frac{\partial \gamma_{xy}}{\partial x} + Y = 0$$

if we express deformations in terms of displacements by expression (1),

$$\frac{E}{1-\mu^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \mu \frac{\partial v}{\partial x \partial y} \right) + \frac{E}{2(1+\mu)} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} \right) + X = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{E}{1-\mu^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + \mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x \partial y} \right) + \frac{E}{2(1+\mu)} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y \partial x} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \right) + Y = 0$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + (1-\mu) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + (1+\mu) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{2(1-\mu^2)}{E} X &= 0 \\ (1+\mu) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + (1-\mu) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{2(1-\mu^2)}{E} Y &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

the equation (13) by differentiating the first one with respect to x the second one y we get

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^3} + (1-\mu) \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x \partial y^2} + (1+\mu) \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x \partial y^2} + (1+\mu) \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^2 \partial y} + \\ + 2 \frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial y^3} + (1-\mu) \frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x^2 \partial y} + \frac{2(1-\mu^2)}{E} \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Y}{\partial y} \right) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^3} + \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x^2 \partial y} + \frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial y^3} + \frac{(1-\mu^2)}{E} \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Y}{\partial y} \right) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \nabla^2 u + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \nabla^2 v + \frac{(1-\mu^2)}{E} \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Y}{\partial y} \right) = 0 \quad (15)$$

this expression ∇^2 through the harmonic operator;

$$\nabla^2 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{(1-\mu^2)}{E} \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Y}{\partial y} \right) = 0 \quad (16)$$

The expression in parentheses u, v represents the displacement and the divergence of the vector of volumetric forces X, Y .

Similarly, if we differentiate the first equation (13) with respect to y the second equation x .

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2\frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^2 \partial y} + (1-\mu)\frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial y^3} + (1+\mu)\frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x \partial y^2} + \frac{2(1-\mu^2)}{E} \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} - \\
 & -(1+\mu)\frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^2 \partial y} - 2\frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x^2 \partial y} - (1-\mu)\frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x^3} - \frac{2(1-\mu^2)}{E} \frac{\partial Y}{\partial y} = 0 \\
 & (1-\mu)\frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^2 \partial y} - (1-\mu)\frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x \partial y^2} + (1-\mu)\frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial y^3} - (1-\mu)\frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x^3} + \frac{2(1-\mu^2)}{E} \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial Y}{\partial y} \right) = 0 \\
 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \right) + \frac{(1+\mu)}{E} \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Y}{\partial y} \right) = 0 \quad (17)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\nabla^2 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{2(1+\mu)}{E} \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial Y}{\partial x} \right) = 0 \quad (18)$$

the expression in parentheses in this equation represents the vector sum of displacement and volume forces.

(16) and (18), we can find the divergence and vector of the displacement vector field we are looking for by certain rules:

from u_1 the homogeneous boundary condition ($u_1 = v_1 = 0$, v_1) on the contour S

$$\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} = d \quad (19)$$

that the sum is zero

$$\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (20)$$

we search in the following form. For the expression (20), the following is appropriate;

$$u_1 = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x}; v_1 = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \quad (21)$$

if we put these expressions in (19),

$$\frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial y^2} = \nabla^2 \varphi = d \quad (22)$$

from here the Poisson equation must be solved for zero boundary conditions.

Similarly (u_2, v_2) divergence of the vector field is zero

$$\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (23)$$

team

$$\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x} = r \quad (24)$$

we find from zero boundary conditions. For the expression (24), the following is appropriate;

$$u_2 = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \quad v_2 = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \quad (25)$$

according to these expressions, (24) ψ can be written through the function,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = \nabla^2 \psi = r \quad (26)$$

In the third case, from the boundary conditions, the field of displacement is zero divergence and the condition is zero

$$\frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_3}{\partial y} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial u_3}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v_3}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (27)$$

to find it is necessary to solve the following equation;

$$\nabla^2 \xi = 0; \quad u_3 = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial y}; \quad v_3 = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x}; \quad (28)$$

or

$$\nabla^2 \eta = 0; \quad u_3 = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x}; \quad v_3 = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y}; \quad (29)$$

The required displacement area (u_1, v_1) is equal to the sum of the areas ,

$$(u_2, v_2), .(u_3, v_3)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We consider a plate in the form of a right rectangle, whose sides under the action of a uniformly distributed load are absolutely rigidly fixed. This satisfies the following boundary conditions.

$$x = 0; \quad x = a \quad \text{for side} \quad w = 0; \quad \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad N_x = 0, \quad v = 0$$

$$y = 0; \quad y = b \quad \text{for side} \quad w = 0; \quad \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0, \quad N_y = 0, \quad v = 0$$

$$(30) \quad \left. \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{E\delta} \nabla^4 \Phi &= \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0 \\ D \nabla^4 w - \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right) &= q \end{aligned} \right\}$$

we look for the solution of the system of equations (30) in the following form.

$$w = \sum_{m,n} f_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{n\pi}{b} y \quad (31)$$

$$\Phi = \sum_{i,j} \varphi_{ij} \sin \frac{i\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{j\pi}{b} y \quad (32)$$

here f_{mn} va φ_{ij} are unchanged. It is not difficult to see that these functions satisfy the boundary conditions. f_{mn} va φ_{ij} we use the Bubnov-Galernin method to determine the invariants.

We put lines (31) and (32) into equations (30), then we multiply the first equation $\sin \frac{i\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{j\pi}{b} y$ by and the second equation $\sin \frac{m\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{n\pi}{b} y$ by .

Integrating each obtained expression over the surface of the plate, we set the result

equal to zero. As a result, f_{mn} $\forall a$ φ_{ij} we have a system of nonlinear algebraic equations with respect to constants.

Simplifying it further, to solve the system of equations (30) we get only one term of the series (31) and (32):

$$\begin{aligned} w &\approx f \sin \frac{\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{\pi}{b} y \\ \Phi &\approx \varphi \sin \frac{\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{\pi}{b} y \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Putting these expressions (33) into (30) we get the following.

$$\begin{aligned} X_1 &= \frac{1}{E\delta} \left(\frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{b^2} \right)^2 \varphi \sin \frac{\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{\pi}{b} y - \\ &- \frac{\pi^4}{a^2 b^2} f \left(\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{a} x \cos^2 \frac{\pi}{b} y - \sin^2 \frac{\pi}{a} x \sin^2 \frac{\pi}{b} y \right); \\ X_2 &= D \left(\frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{b^2} \right)^2 f \sin \frac{\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{\pi}{b} y - \\ &- 2 \frac{\pi^4}{a^2 b^2} \varphi \left(\sin^2 \frac{\pi}{a} x \sin^2 \frac{\pi}{b} y - \cos^2 \frac{\pi}{a} x \cos^2 \frac{\pi}{b} y \right) - q. \end{aligned}$$

Using the Bubnov-Galernin method, we integrate X_1 and X_2 over the surface of the plate by multiplying by $f \sin \frac{\pi}{a} x \sin \frac{\pi}{b} y$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{b^2} \right)^2 \varphi + \frac{16\pi^4 E\delta}{3a^2 b^2} f^2 &= 0 \\ D \left(\frac{\pi^2}{a^2} + \frac{\pi^2}{b^2} \right)^2 f - \frac{32\pi^4}{3a^2 b^2} f\varphi &= \frac{16}{\pi^2} q \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (34)$$

(34) comes to the equation with respect to one f . For example $\frac{a}{b} = 1$

$$\frac{1}{\delta} + \frac{128(1-\mu^2)}{3\pi^4} \cdot \frac{f^3}{\delta^3} = B \quad (35)$$

$$\text{here } B = \frac{4qa^4}{\pi^6 D \delta}$$

(35), we analyze the problem of bending of a flexible square plate. The more accurate the solution depends on taking more terms of the series (31) and (32).

The problem is given as follows solutions in numerical values are described in graphs: $h:=0.01$; $a:=1$; $b:=1$; $n:=0.17$; $q:=200$; $\pi:=3.14$; $E:=4*10^{10}$; $x:=1/2$; $W:=0.00012*\sin(\pi*x/a)*\sin(\pi*y/b)$;

Figure 2. $q := 200$ pa strength when placed W is flexible of displacement and 2- hard plate variation slopes in the y coordinate when $x=a/2$ graphics. It can be seen from the graphs that as the value of the external force increases, the difference between the deflections of the flexible plate and the rigid plate increases.

CONCLUSION

Numerical experiments were conducted to study the processes of deformation and transverse vibrations of a thin rectangular plate whose edges are arbitrarily drawn under the influence of uniformly distributed loads on the surface, and the obtained numerical results were analyzed .

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